

Research

Drone Survey in the Mountainous Region of Nepal

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Accepted: 1 October , 2020; **Online:** 05 October, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4065326>

Abstract We present a system to utilize a UAV (automated aeronautical vehicle) to perform photogrammetric overviews and itemized geographical planning in mountain zones. This work is uniquely identified with the given contextual investigation the mean to acknowledge geomorphological guides from UAVs, since they can house various kinds of sensors and secure information more quickly and economically than customary topographical overviews legitimately got with field perceptions. This work clarifies how UAVs can acquire computerized territory models, orthophotos and 3D models so as to make incline and angle maps for land purposes. By incorporating information from UAVs with geographical reviews made on the field, topographical guides can be created where a large number of the land components are introduced. This paper presents the coordination of geomatics and topographical procedures. Beginning from UAV slant map and orthophotos, another land map was made in a quicker and more definite manner contrasted with customary geographical review on the ground. The utilization of this strategy respects a segment of the Nepal, framed by icy masses and profound situated gravitational slant misshapenings.

Keywords: Nepal, Mountains, Drone, UAV

1. Introduction

Topographical planning is a complex and tedious movement, particularly when done in mountain regions, where there are high slants (Fischer et al. 2012; Joyce et al. 2014). Albeit master geologists can do ground planning, they don't generally accomplish a total review of the region. In addition, such 'conventional planning' (topographical review: lithological development, auxiliary and

geomorphological components, and so forth.) doesn't explore all the properties of the territory, for example, any water content.

Then again, by covering a huge region in brief timeframe (ca. 60 ha/h), automated flying vehicles (UAVs) can get information more quickly and less lavishly than common airborne reviews. Business UAVs (Sadeghipoor et al. 2015) regularly gain RGB (Endres et al. 2014) and close infrared (NIR) pictures (Chen et al. 2015). Utilizing a photogrammetric approach, advanced surface models (DSMs), computerized territory models (DTMs) (Dabove et al. 2015) and orthophotos (Guarnieri et al. 2015) can be created consequently. Incline and perspective guides can likewise be separated from DTMs, which are helpful for looking at the territory and extricating the geographical guide.

The last items give geologists a more complete and broadened perspective, which would then be able to be utilized to check the quality and legitimacy of information gathered in the field utilizing customary studies.

The land data gathered by conventional topographical planning got in the field is utilized to think about a similar data which is recognized by these guides. As of now, numerous cartographic geographical items are gotten by coupling satellite pictures (frequently with low goal) and field reviews, which is tedious and requires exceptionally exact information on the land region.

Topographical examination with UAVs is done everywhere on the world, and misusing UAVs for land applications is normal. Actually, UAVs have decreased the hour of land reviews, while keeping up the nature of subtleties (Bemis et al. 2014). UAVs are frequently utilized for territorial exploration, for example, domain investigation (Farfaglia et al. 2015), avalanche checking (Torrero et al. 2015), disfigurement investigation (Shi and Liu 2015), planning land structures at a little scope (Vasuki et al. 2014), and furthermore for checking geothermal situations (Nishar et al. 2016). Notwithstanding, supposedly, UAVs have not been utilized for point by point topographical overviews. We utilized a UAV to plan a part of the Rodoretto Valley, a left feeder of the Germanasca Valley, situated in the Nepal on the Greenstone and Schist (GS) Complex of the Penninic Domain (Figure 1). The zone explored was framed by ice sheets and profound situated gravitational slant distortions.

Figure 1. Aeronautical picture of the examination zone (An) and western land map altered by Mattiolo et al. (1913) (B), where the star speaks to the examination region.

Depiction of the system and geomatics exercises

As depicted in Eisenbeiss (2009), two perspectives must be considered before completing an aerial photograph utilizing UAV: the decision of the procurement framework and the information preparing technique, which are major for the picture cover and the normal ground test separation (GSD).

The decision of the procurement framework (fixed-winged or multi-rotor UAV) relies upon the kind of movement that will be made, since they have various exhibitions regarding payload, flight time and security in information obtaining. For instance, for photogrammetric purposes, a fixed-wing UAV is best in wide zones (1.5 km range), while multi-rotor UAVs are more reasonable for littler zones (400 × 400m) or where vertical flight is required (Giordan et al. 2015).

The information handling methodology should consider arranging the flight, characterizing the study region, the quantity of lines and the relative flight height.

Information securing is key since it incorporates trips as well as estimating the vertex of the reference network through a geographical (absolute station or GNSS) overview and the assurance of ground control focuses (which are utilized for the georeferencing – Chiabrando et al. 2013). The

last stage is information preparing, which incorporates photogrammetric triangulation (picture arrangement for the 3D point cloud age), 3D model reproduction, the DSM and orthophotos extraction, and information combination.

Prior to beginning the flight methodology, first, the ground studies should be dissected. So as to characterize the directions of the ground control focuses that were utilized to georeference the orthophotos and DSM, we made and estimated a geodetic organization by utilizing both GNSS and conventional geological (complete station) reviews.

The GNSS lobby was directed utilizing twofold recurrence and multi-heavenly body beneficiaries and considering both a post-preparing (Dabove et al. 2014) and a RTK (constant kinematic, with radio association for ongoing amendments) approaches, because of the absence of the GSM signal. Subsequently, an ace station was set up (for a meeting length of over four hours) on a point that was named GPS1 so as to have a known point with millimetrical exactness. This point was then used to change different markers.

The directions of this station were dictated by a post-preparing approach, thinking about a solitary base arrangement (got with the Leica Geo Office v.8.4, Leica Geosystems®) with a Virtual RINEX made by the nonstop working reference stations (CORSSs) of the Piedmont local government (Dabove and Manzano 2014). A RTK study with radio association was then made so as to appraise markers with no leaf inclusion (prefix 0 in Figure 2), considering a meeting length of around 10 s for each point. The directions were assessed with a centimeter exactness ($\sigma = 3$ cm) with fixed-stage ambiguities for all focuses, which guaranteed an elevated level of accuracy for the georeferencing cycle. Now and again, where the leaf inclusion was very high, target focuses were estimated by customary geological instruments (prefix I in Figure 2). For this situation, the absolute station was determined to the mount of the GNSS ace station (point GPS1) so as to gauge all the rest of the markers, because of a reflector. All the estimations were accordingly balanced (following the base limitations approach) with MicroSurvey StarNet v.7.0, so as to get the last organizes of the GCPs (ground control focuses): the root mean square (RMS) acquired with StarNet is under 1 cm.

Figure 2. Focuses procured by GNSS (with prefix 0) and all out station (with prefix I) instruments acquired after the post-handling.

UAV flight with RGB camera

The resolution of the model or the data update sometimes entails integrating the map with additional data, both aerial and terrestrial. UAVs can be now used to acquire aerial information (RGB, multispectral, NIR images) in order to create 3D models and to make a land classification.

It is essential to choose the best solution in relation to the specific case study (Boccardo et al. 2015). For this application, due to the large area involved and the ground shape, we use an eBee, which is a commercial fixed-wings solution made by Sensefly. An eBee can fly for up to 40 minutes, with a coverage of 35–40 ha and it does not require a runway or expert users, because take-off and landing are completely automatic. The main technical and operational characteristics of this system are reported in Table 1.

Table 1

Technical specifications		Operative specifications	
Weight (camera included)	0.69 kg	Maximum flight time	50 min
Dimension	55 × 45 × 25 cm	Flight velocity	50-90 km/h
Wingspan	96 cm	Radio-link range	3 km
Propulsion	Electric, DC 160 W brushless motors	Maximum surface detectable	12 km ² at 974 m of altitude
Battery	11.1 V, 2150 mAh	Ground sampling distance at 100 m	0.03 m

3D model generation and data integration

The aim of the photogrammetric acquisition was to produce an orthophoto and a dense DSM (DDSM) with a high resolution (4 cm) in order to integrate the existing spatial data to perform geological mapping.

All the acquired images were post-processed using a structure from motion (SFM) approach (Turner et al. 2012) to rapidly and accurately extract a 3D model from images (Westoby et al. 2012). In this case, the processing was performed using two different commercial solutions (Mendes et al. 2015):

- Menci APS (Automatic Photogrammetric Station): which is an image processing software application for mapping and modelling, and which comes with the eBee (<http://www.menci.com/photogrammetry-software/aps-3d-maps-software>);
- Agisoft PhotoScan: this is one of the most popular commercial solutions for 3D reconstructions starting from digital images (<http://www.agisoft.com/>).

Both these software applications follow a specific workflow for generating the model (Remondino et al. 2014):

- image alignment and point cloud generation: this defines the position of the image in a local coordinates system starting from the tie points extraction (usually through the SIFT operator). It generates a sparse point cloud (Aicardi et al. 2014);

- 3D coloured model: starting from the point cloud, a triangulated irregular network (TIN) mesh is generated;
- model georeferencing: with both applications, the model can be georeferenced in a chosen reference system; this is possible through the use of approximate external orientation parameters acquired by the UAV during the flight or through targets (GCPs) to improve the accuracy. In this case, we use the second method, in which some points were used also for the model validation. In particular, five of them were used as control points showing a final accuracy of about 5 cm;
- generation of photogrammetric products: a DDSM (Figure 3) and an orthophoto (Figure 4) are generated. They are coloured, georeferenced and with a resolution of 4 cm (Teeravech 2015).

Figure 3. DSM and orthophotos in 3D view generated through the SfM approach.

At long last, the utilization of a strong (valid) Orthophoto (Forno et al. 2012) gives a total 3-D land information interface and a right ethereal photographic viewpoint in a geo-referred to frame, which on location, during the review, were exceptionally valuable (Forno et al. 2011).

Geologists untalented in geomatics have productively utilized these new instruments during field reviews. The 3-D perception encouraged the quick translation of relict landforms with: time investment funds during obtaining and stacking into GIS programming; less mistakes accordingly blocking the requirement for rehashed surveillance and which likewise accelerates map creations; better comprehension of the morphological proof with the accessibility of 3D mathematical data coordinated with 2D sees like what the assessor sees.

Investigation of the models and results

The portrayed technique with UAV was applied in the examined region to assess whether this methodology could support the geographical study, accordingly permitting us to assemble a more extensive application model.

The incline guide can outfit data for speaking to morphological and topographical proof. The chance of utilizing this portrayal is carefully adapted by past land studies of the territory, which implies that the different incline changes can be alluded to a regular geographical setting. The vast majority of the topographical understandings are additionally upheld by the perceptions of orthophoto and DSM got from airborne photographs taken during the flight and furthermore incline maps created from them. This implies the perceived incline changes can be perused, which is especially helpful in the generally unavailable zones.

The contextual analysis was an icy valley with steep rough mountain sides and a wide level valley floor secured with subglacial and supraglacial residue. The gravitational marvels including this region are obvious from numerous gravitational components, for example, cracks, minor scarps and channels (Forno et al. 2012). The created slant map covers a part of the left slant (northern region in Figure 7) and the wide valley floor (southern zone in Figure 7). The definite geologic information on the region permitted us to univocally peruse the slant map.

A general translation of the incline map assists with understanding the appropriation of the bedrock and Quaternary silt. Steep parts obvious in this guide (Figure 8) relate to shake outcrops on the left side, on the grounds that solitary the bedrock makes sharp dividers. The level divisions (Figure 8)

relate to the territories secured by frigid silt, on the wide valley floor. The medium incline parts (Figure 8) relate to the mountain side and valley floor regions without bedrock outcrops however secured by meager colluvium.

A more itemized understanding of the incline guide can, notwithstanding by and large perceptions, help to plan the direct topographical components indicating a quick morphological reaction (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Morphological and Quaternary geographical guide of the Rodoretto Valley. 1: minor scarp; 2: channel; 3: scarp associated with heavy entry point; 4: heavy cut reused by torrential slide wonders; 5: torrential slide fan; 6: separation specialty; 7: avalanche collection limit; 8: moraine pivot; 9: outwash cut.

Conclusion

The consequences of this examination feature the value of the UAV framework in the age of 3D aeronautical data for topographical purposes. UAVs can be utilized to plan the territory of intrigue quickly and at a generally minimal effort, and give high-goal results. What's more, the likelihood to utilize these high-goal information to make slants map implies that the ground elements saw on the field can be distinguished and surveyed.

The incline map gives helpful data for the land planning of a cold valley, given the morphological reaction of the geographical components is known through the topographical overview. UAVs combined with merged geomatics strategies can help in the nitty gritty planning of the different components in the to a great extent unavailable territories. Moreover, these frameworks can secure

various types of information, which would then be able to be joined so as to feature concealed land subtleties.

Airborne photographs taken from UAVs and incline maps are especially helpful for recognizing the fundamental straight land components (minor scarps, channels, heavy and torrential slide entry points, separation specialties and aggregations, moraine pivot and icy cuts). These photographs empowered us to make another definite geomorphological review of the Rodoretto Valley Quaternary. The examination recorded different sorts of various geographical components which in a conventional topographical overview are exceptionally hard to recognize because of the presence of vegetation or incline sides which are hard to get to (breaks, channels, minor scarps). The planning of the ethereal geographical components, with the appropriation of bedrock and Quaternary residue, needs, rather, more nitty gritty land field perceptions and the utilization of different guides, for example, NIR pictures.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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